

To Compare the Effect of Expressed Breast Milk (EBM) Versus 10% Dextrose on Procedural Pain in Term Neonates – A Double-Blind Randomized Control Trial in a Rural Teaching Hospital in Telangana

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Abstract:

Objective: To compare the effect of expressed breast milk (EBM), versus 10% dextrose on procedural pain in neonates as assessed by the Neonatal Infant Pain Scale (NIPS), changes in heart rate (HR), oxygen saturation (SpO₂) and duration of crying.

Design: Prospective, double blind randomized controlled trial.

Setting: Postnatal ward of a tertiary-care hospital.

Participants: 60 neonates who required heel prick were recruited into the study according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria after written parental informed consent.

Methods: The enrolled neonates were randomized into intervention groups –EBM and 10% Dextrose. Two ml of test solution was given to baby by paladary 2 minutes before heel prick by a nurse. The heel prick was later administered by one of the blinded investigators. The face and crying of baby were video graphed by another blinded investigator. The facial response to pain was analyzed from the video. Outcome variable: NIPS score, heart rates and SpO₂ at pre procedure. 30 seconds, 2 minutes and 4 minutes and duration of cry were recorded.

Results: 60 babies were considered for final analysis with 30 in 10% D, and 30 in EBM group. The median NIPS score of neonates in EBM group was 4 at 30 seconds while it was 6 in the 10% D group which was statistically significant. The duration of cry in the EBM group (44.53 ± 28.63 seconds) was lower than that of 10% D group (52.46±43.58) though not statistically significant. On subgroup analysis, there was a significant difference between NIPS scores (p<0.00001) across the timelines in each group. There was a significant change in heart rate across the timelines in each group (p<0.00001).

Conclusions: This study has established that both 10%D and expressed breast milk are efficacious in reducing pain in neonates. More studies are required on a larger scale to identify the best non pharmacological agent/method and set up robust clinical guidelines to be followed uniformly in all NICUs.

Keywords: 10% dextrose, Expressed breast milk, Neonatal pain, NIPS score.

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Introduction

Neonates undergo many painful interventions during their stay in neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) that include nasogastric tube insertion, heel pricks, intravenous cannula placement, endotracheal intubation and various others. Among these, heel prick procedure is routinely done for monitoring capillary blood glucose to detect hypoglycemia in

low birth weight (LBW) neonates and infants of diabetic mothers (IDM).[1] Emerging evidence suggests that repetitive painful procedures can have detrimental effects on the long-term neurological development of neonates, with animal studies showing that early life pain can increase glucocorticoid receptors in the hippocampus,

potentially affecting future stress responses.[2] Pharmacological methods are the most often used methods to ameliorate pain in infants. However, many analgesics have adverse effects needing the exploration of non-pharmacological alternatives. These include non-nutritive sucking (NNS), breastfeeding (BF), dextrose solution, skin-to-skin care (SSC), KMC (Kangaroo mother care), swaddling, therapeutic massage, musical therapy (MT) and facilitated tucking which activate a “gate control mechanism” that prevents the pain sensation from traveling to the central nervous system.[3] Breast milk is found to contain increased amount of tryptophan, a precursor of melatonin. Melatonin increases β endorphins which play a role in reducing pain intensity while sucrose decreases pain via opioid mechanisms.[3]

Among the non-pharmacological agents, the sugar solutions and breast milk in the form of BF or Expressed breast milk (EBM) have been often studied. Multiple studies point towards 25%D being able to significantly reduce pain in neonates. [4,5,6]. However, Collados -Gómez L et al. and Naik A et al. reported no significant difference in the analgesic effect between breast milk and sucrose over pain intensity in preterm neonates.[7,8] Further, Sahoo J P et al. and Vohra A et al. have demonstrated that EBM is efficacious in reducing pain in neonates better than 25%D. [9,10] But using 25%D in neonates may produce side effects like vomiting and feed intolerance due to the high osmolarity of the solution as has been observed by Rawal S et al. [6]

Hence, 10%D has been compared to EBM by multiple clinicians with varied results ranging from them being equally efficacious[3,11] to 10%D faring better than EBM.[12] Though studies have been published about interventions in reducing pain in neonates, robust evidence is still not available, [13] which harbors need for further studies need to be conducted. This would help in formulation of clear guidelines for use in NICU which will be beneficial to the newborns who cannot verbalize their pain, and depend on others to recognize, assess, and treat their pain.

The primary objective of the trial was to compare the effect of expressed breast milk (EBM) vs 10% Dextrose (10%D) over intensity of pain in term neonates using NIPS scale (Neonatal Infant Pain Scale). Comparison of the duration of cry along with changes in physiological variables like heart rate and SpO₂ between both groups was also planned.

Methods

This study was a double blinded, parallel group randomized controlled trial approved by the institutional ethics committee. (Approval/ MIMS/ EC/16/IV/2K21(6/9)). The trial was registered at Clinical Trials Registry- India (CTRI/2021/06/03 4053- Trial Registered Prospectively). The trial was

conducted among neonates in the postnatal wards of Mediciti Institute of Medical Sciences (MIMS). All neonates who were born at MIMS during the period between 15th June 2021 to 30th June 2022 and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were eligible for the study.

Inclusion Criteria

Term healthy neonates (neonates ≥ 37 weeks of gestational age) requiring heel prick procedure for monitoring hypoglycemia, as in LBW neonates and IDM.

Exclusion Criteria-

1. Neonates who require resuscitation at birth.
2. Neonates on Life support like CPAP/ ventilator.
3. Neonates with congenital anomalies pertaining to head and face - cleft lip/palate.
4. Sick neonates-sepsis, neonatal seizures.
5. Neonates whose parents refuse to provide consent for the study.

The sample size was calculated based on a similar earlier study by Malngiang et al.[12] The mean duration of cry in one group was 4.77 seconds with standard deviation of 1.5 seconds. The other group had a mean of 3.66 seconds and standard deviation of 0.94 seconds. Based on duration of cry, [12] with power 90 and alpha (two sided) as 5, the sample size for each group of the trial was calculated to be 27 neonates and rounded off to 30. (30 neonates in group receiving EBM & 30 neonates in group receiving 10% Dextrose; an allocation ratio of 1:1).

Interventions & Procedure

The intervention was administration of 2ml of 10% Dextrose orally to one group and 2ml of expressed breast milk orally to another group prior to procedure of heel prick. 10% Dextrose solution was procured from pharmacy. Expressed breast milk of neonate's mother was taken from his/her mother.

The procedure was done as explained below. Randomization was done using computer software. Allocation concealment was achieved by sequentially numbered opaque sealed envelopes containing the codes for intervention by a person not involved in the study. Neonates were selected by postnatal ward consultant who was aware of the inclusion and exclusion criteria but did not take part in the further steps of trial.

The procedure was performed in Precht stage 4/5 of quiet wakefulness state of the baby. Throughout the procedure (duration 20 minutes) the neonate was placed under radiant warmer in the postnatal ward to ensure adequate warmth and comfort. Neonates were fed 1 hour prior to the procedure and diapers were changed. These neonates underwent heel prick procedure [14] as one time procedure.

Two ml of the intervention solution was administered by a paladay orally to the baby by a trained staff nurse after opening the opaque envelope assigned to the baby which had the code of intervention solution. Here only the nurse knew the intervention solution.

After the intervention solution was administered orally, all the syringes/ paladay were removed from the warmer before the investigators were called. Heel prick was performed two minutes after intervention.

Investigator 1 who was blinded to the intervention, documented the baseline heart rate, SPO₂, using a monitor before the procedure. Following standard operating procedure guidelines, the nurse performed the heel prick on the outer aspect of the heel using 26 G lancet. After documenting blood sugar, hemostasis was achieved, and neonate monitored for 15 minutes. Investigator 2, who was also blinded, recorded videos of the neonates. Behavioral responses of the neonate before starting the procedure till 5 minutes post procedure were

recorded. NIPS score was assigned to the neonate before the heel prick procedure (baseline), at 30 secs, 2 minutes and 4 minutes of the procedure and documented by observer 2 based on the videos. Investigator 2 was experienced in NIPS assessment with prior training to decrease intra and inter-observer variations. NIPS scale is a pain assessment score used worldwide to grade pain intensity based on facial expression, cry, breathing pattern, position of arms and legs and state of arousal. A score of ≥ 2 indicates pain.

Outcomes: The duration of the cry and the NIPS scores, heart rate and SpO₂ at 30 seconds, 2 minutes and 4 minutes were recorded. Digital stopwatch was used to maintain the accuracy of timing.

Assessment Tool: Neonatal infant pain scale (NIPS) - (Figure 1) It consists of six indicators: five behavioral and one physiological indicator. It is scored with a 0,1 or 2. Interpretation- 0–1: no pain; 2: mild pain; 3–4: moderate pain; 5–7: severe pain.

Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale (NIPS)

(Recommended for children less than 1 year old) A score greater than 3 indicates pain.

Pain Assessment		Score
Facial Expression		
0 - Relaxed Muscles	Restful face, neutral expression	
1 - Grimace	Tight facial muscles; furrowed brow, chin, jaw (negative facial expression – nose, mouth brow)	
Cry		
0 - No cry	Quiet, not crying	
1 - Whimper	Mild moaning, intermittent	
2 - Vigorous cry	Loud scream; rising, shrill, continuous (Note: Silent cry may be scored if baby is intubated as evidenced by obvious mouth and facial movement)	
Breathing Pattern		
0 - Relaxed	Usual pattern for this infant	
1 - Change in breathing	Indrawing, irregular, faster than usual; gagging, breath holding	
Arms		
0 - Relaxed/Restrained	No Muscular rigidity; occasional random movements of arms	
1 - Flexed/Extended	Tense, straight arms; rigid and/or rapid extension, flexion	
Legs		
0 - Relaxed/Restrained	No Muscular rigidity; occasional random movements of legs	
1 - Flexed/Extended	Tense, straight legs; rigid and/or rapid extension, flexion	
State of Arousal		
0 - Sleeping/Awake	Quiet, peaceful, sleeping or alert, random leg movements	
1 - Fussy	Alert, restless and thrashing	

Figure 1: Neonatal/ Infant Pain Scale

Statistical Analysis

The data was recorded and analyzed by using SPSS software version 22.0 (SPSS inc., Chicago, IL USA). Normality was tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Differences in means were compared using repeated measures ANOVA for parametric data and Friedman’s test for non-parametric data. Independent T-tests and Mann-Whitney tests were used to compare group differences, with a p-value of <0.05 being considered statistically significant.

Results

Neonates were selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria and randomized to both the groups. A total of 30 neonates were randomized to each group from the recruitment period of June 15th2021 to December 6th2021. All the randomized neonates underwent the necessary intervention and were analyzed for the primary outcome. No losses were reported after randomization in each group.

Figure 1 provides the algorithm related to selection of neonates for the study. Table 1 provides the basic demographic details of the neonates randomized to both the groups.

Figure 1: Flowchart summarizing the trial profile and participant flow

Table 1: Basic Demographic details of neonates

S. No	Characteristics	Expressed Breast Milk (n=30)	10% Dextrose group (n=30)	P value
1.	Mean weight (SD) (grams)	2477.83(360.56)	2373.63(403.59)	0.148 (Independent T test)
2.	Mean GA (SD) (weeks)	38.3 (0.988)	37.833 (0.87)	0.0288 (Independent T test)
3.	Number of male neonates	14	17	0.6058(Fisher exact)
4.	Neonates born to mothers with diabetes complicating pregnancy	11	6	0.0539 (Fisher Exact)
5.	Neonates with low birth weight (LBW)	16	24	0.252 (Fisher Exact)
6.	Neonates born LBW and to mother with diabetes complicating pregnancy	3	0	-

There was a significant change in heart rate across the timelines in each group ($p < 0.00001$). But between the two groups, the change in heart rate and SPO₂ was not statistically significant. Table 2 provides the data of heart rate and SPO₂ at various time periods for both the groups.

Table 2: Mean heart rate and SPO₂ at various timelines of procedure for both the groups

Variables assessed Mean (SD)	Expressed Breast Milk Group (n=30)	10% Dextrose Group (n=30)	P value by Independent T test
Mean HR Pre Procedure (SD)	145.8 (13.45)	140 (13.13)	0.0482
Mean HR at 30 seconds (SD)	156.5 (17.19)	150.6 (13.51)	0.0735
Mean HR at 2 minutes (SD)	144.6 (18.02)	138.6 (18.52)	0.10306
Mean HR at 4 minutes (SD)	134.2 (13.78)	126.4 (15.43)	0.02043
Mean SPO ₂ pre procedure (SD)	96.8 (2.23)	97.2 (2.05)	0.2746
Mean SPO ₂ at 30 seconds (SD)	96.3 (2.67)	97.1 (1.86)	0.10038
Mean SPO ₂ at 2 minutes (SD)	96.2 (2.87)	96.6 (2.29)	0.2936
Mean SPO ₂ at 4 minutes (SD)	96.1 (3.40)	96.9 (2.30)	0.1452

HR: Heart rate; SD: standard deviation

The NIPS score of the neonates at various timelines and the duration of cry was compared across the two groups.

The duration of cry was lower in EBM group than 10%D group but was not statistically significant. The NIPS score at 30 sec was significantly different ($p=0.0197$) between both the groups; the neonates who received 2ml of 10% Dextrose had higher

median NIPS scores compared to the neonate in the EBM group.

There was no significant difference observed in NIPS scores across other timelines. Table3 shows the median NIPS scores and the mean duration of cry across the two groups. The range of NIPS scores across 30 seconds, 1 minute and 2 minutes is shown in figure 2.

Table 3: Median NIPS score and mean duration of cry in both the groups

Variables assessed	Expressed Breast Milk Group (n=30)	10% Dextrose group (n=30)	P value (Mann - Whitney)
Median NIPS Pre Procedure	0	0.5	0.6818
Median NIPS at 30 sec	4	6	0.0197
Median NIPS at 2 min	1	1.5	0.6818
Median NIPS at 4 min	0	0	0.9920
Mean (SD) of duration of cry (in seconds)	44.53(28.63)	52.46(43.58)	0.2049*

* Independent T Test; NIPS: Neonatal Infant Pain Score; SD: standard deviation

On subgroup analysis, there was a significant difference between NIPS scores across the timelines in each group. Both EBM and 10%D had brought about a significant lowering of pain scores across the timelines. Table 4 shows the Friedmann test for NIPS scores of both groups. There were no untoward accidents or adverse events that happened to any of the randomized neonates warranting withdrawal or stoppage of the trial.

Figure 2: Distribution of NIPS score of neonates across various timelines of procedure

NIPS: Neonatal Infant Pain Score; EBM: Expressed Breast Milk

Table 4: Median NIPS scores at various timelines of both groups

Variables assessed	Median NIPS Pre Procedure	Median NIPS at 30 seconds	Median NIPS at 2 minutes	Median NIPS at 4 minutes	P value (Friedmann Test for repeated measures)
Expressed Breast Milk Group (n=30)	0	4	1	0	<0.00001
10% Dextrose group (n=30)	0.5	6	1.5	0	<0.00001

Discussion

This study showed that both 10% dextrose and EBM decreased pain response in neonates as assessed by NIPS scale. This analgesic effect of 10% D or EBM is probably based on the link that is theorized to exist between the Oro-Gustatory effect of sweet solution and the endogenous opioid pathway.[15] The analgesic effect of breast milk is also related to the higher concentration of melatonin that increases the concentration of beta endorphins. [16,17] In this study, we preferred to use glucose over sucrose as it is easily and widely available in all neonatal units in India. Further, we opted to use 10% D in this study, as 25%D is hyperosmolar and can possibly result in feed intolerance, vomiting, NEC and hyperglycemia requiring monitoring for up to 48 hours.

In this study, the intensity of pain perceived was significantly less in the EBM group compared to 10%D at the first 30 seconds of procedure. Vohra et al. [10] observed that neonates given 0.5 ml of EBM had reduced mean PIPP (Premature Infant Pain Profile) scores compared to equal amount of 24% sucrose solution before the immunization procedure. Similar analgesic properties of EBM have been reported by Jatana SK et al. [4] where they had compared EBM against multiple concentration of dextrose. They had, however, used 1 ml of all the intervention solutions. Like the present study, Hsieh KH [11] et al. observed that 10% D and EBM had equally efficacious response in bringing down the pain intensity in preterm neonates. They also observed that severe pain was observed between 0-30 seconds of procedure akin to this study.

We observed that the NIPS scores were lesser in EBM group than 10%D group at all the times and the mean duration of cry was lesser in EBM group though not statistically significant. Sahoo JP et al. [9] studied pain response using PIPP (Premature infant Pain Profile) scores and compared the effect of EBM, 25%D and sterile water on pain response among neonates. They observed no significant difference in the duration of cry and PIPP scores at 30 seconds of procedure. Certain other studies have compared 25%D and EBM and found that 25%D to have better antinociceptive action than EBM [5,6] while a study by Malngiang B et al. [12] observed decreased duration of cry and NIPS scores with 10%D compared to EBM. In the study done by Malngiang B et al. [12], the authors have not provided whether uniformity of timelines were

maintained as to when the NIPS was administered to the neonates.

The strengths of this study include use of a validated and reliable tool for assessment of pain in term neonates i.e NIPS scale, [18] blinding of both investigators to the interventions involved, and no exclusions post randomization. The limitations of the study are that we did not study the effect on multiple punctures, small sample size and non-generalizability to sick neonates.

Conclusion

This study has established that both 10%D and expressed breast milk are efficacious in reducing pain in neonates. More studies are required on a larger scale to identify the best nonpharmacological agent/method and establish robust clinical guidelines to be followed uniformly in all NICUs.

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References

1. Screening guidelines for newborns at risk for low blood glucose. *Paediatr Child Health*. 2004; 9(10):723-740.
2. Meaney M.J., Aitken D.H. The effects of early postnatal handling on hippocampal glucocorticoid receptor concentrations: Temporal parameters. *Brain Res*. 1985; 354:301-304.
3. Melzack R., Wall P.D. Pain mechanism: A new theory. *Science*. 1965; 150:971-979.
4. Jatana SK, Dalal SS, Wilson CG. Analgesic Effect of Oral Glucose in Neonates. *Med J Armed Forces Ind*. 2003; 59(2):100-4.
5. Varghese TC, Paul AS, Soans S. Oral dextrose v/s breast milk for the pain relief of newborn infants. *Clin. Invest. (Lond.)*. 2020; 10(3), 90-94.
6. Rawal S, Ghai A, & Jindal T. Twenty-Five Percent Dextrose and EBM in Pain Relief During Heel Lance in Late Preterm Babies Using the PIPP Score: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Neonatol*. 2018; 32(2-3): 43-49.
7. Collados-Gómez L, Ferrera-Camacho P, Fernandez-Serrano E et al. Randomised crossover trial showed that using breast milk or sucrose

- provided the same analgesic effect in preterm infants of at least 28 weeks. *Acta Paediatr.* 2018 Mar; 107(3):436-441.
8. Naik A, D'Lima A, Sreekumar K, Silveira MP. Efficacy of Expressed Breast Milk Alone or in Combination with Paracetamol in Reducing Pain during ROP Screening: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Clin Neonatol.*2021; 10(2): 73-78.
 9. Sahoo JP, Rao S, Nesargi S et al. Expressed Breast Milk vs 25% Dextrose in Procedural Pain in Neonates: A Double Blind Randomized Controlled Trial. *Ind Pediatr.* 2013; 50: 203-207.
 10. Vohra A, Purani C, Mehariya K M, Shah B. Neonatal Analgesia: Effect of Sucrose Solution versus Breastfeeding in Procedural Pain. *Pediatr Oncall J.* 2017; 14: 79-81.
 11. Hsieh KH, Chen SJ, Tsao PC et al. The analgesic effect of non-pharmacological interventions to reduce procedural pain in preterm neonates. *Pediatr Neonatol.*2018.59:71-76.
 12. Malngiang B, Singh S, Golmei N, et al. A comparative study between expressed breast milk and oral glucose for the relief of pain in newborns undergoing skin pricking procedures. *IOSR J Dent Med Sci.* 2016; 15(3):28-32.
 13. American Academy of Pediatrics, Committee on Fetus and Newborn, Section on Anesthesiology and Pain Medicine, Canadian Paediatric Society, Fetus and Newborn Committee. (2016). Prevention and Management of Procedural Pain in the Neonate: An Update. *Pediatrics*, 137(2), e20154271.
 14. WHO Guidelines on Drawing Blood: Best Practices in Phlebotomy. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2010.7, Capillary sampling. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK138654/>
 15. Gradin M, Schollin J. The role of endogenous opioids in mediating pain reduction by orally administered glucose among newborns. *Pediatrics.* 2005; 115(4):1004–7.
 16. Blass EM. Milk-induced hypoalgesia in human newborns. *Pediatrics.* 1997; 99: 825–9.
 17. Barrett T, Kent S, Voudouris N. Does melatonin modulate beta-endorphin, corticosterone and pain threshold? *Life Sci.* 2000; 66:467-76.
 18. Hala Obiedat and Effat Ibrahim Al-Maaitah (2020) Critique of the Use of Neonatal Infant Pain Scale (NIPS). *Neonat Pediatr Med* 6: 186.